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Supporting Information for

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Nanogoethite as a potential indicator of remagnetization in red beds

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Contents of this file

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Text S1, Figures S1 to S6, Tables S1 to S6

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21

Introduction

22

This file contains one text, six figures and six tables further detailing the Nangqian red beds samples and their tests results described in the manuscript.

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Text S1. Methods

25

Magnetic hysteresis loops, back field curves and isothermal remanent magnetization (IRM) acquisition curves were made using a Princeton Measurements MicroMag

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27 vibrating-sample magnetometer (VSM, nominal sensitivity of $5 \times 10^{-9} \text{ Am}^2$, maximum
28 applied field of 1.4 T) on 35 samples (eight type A samples, 18 type B samples, and
29 nine type C samples, [Table S1](#)) at room temperature at the Institute for Rock
30 Magnetism at the University of Minnesota (USA), and Utah Paleomagnetic Center at
31 the University of Utah (USA).

32

33 IRM component analyses on 31 samples ([Table S2](#)) were applied using MAX UnMix,
34 described in *Maxbauer et al.* [2016]. The analysis results are the coercivity spectra
35 which display derivatives of the isothermal remanent magnetization curves with
36 respect to $\log_{10}(\text{field})$. High-temperature, low-field magnetic susceptibility
37 measurements were performed in air on 17 whole-rock samples (five type A samples,
38 six type B samples, and six type C samples, [Table S3](#)) using a KLY-2 KappaBridge
39 AC susceptibility meter with an AC field of 300 A/m and a frequency of 920 Hz at the
40 Institute for Rock Magnetism and Utah Paleomagnetic Center. Four cycles of
41 successive heating to 300°C, 500°C, 600°C, and 700°C with intervening cooling to
42 room temperature were carried out on each sample.

43

44 Low-temperature alternating current (AC) susceptibility and remanence experiments
45 were run on a Quantum Design Magnetic Properties Measurement System (MPMS) at
46 the Institute for Rock Magnetism. One sample (14NQ0409) was run for
47 low-temperature susceptibility measurements at five frequencies (1.0, 5.6, 31.6, 177.9,
48 and 997.3 Hz). For the low-temperature remanence measurements, samples (six type
49 A samples, eight type B samples, and five type C samples, [Table S4](#)) were given a
50 room-temperature saturation isothermal remanent magnetization (RTSIRM) in 2.5 T,
51 and then measured in zero field during cooling to 20 K and on rewarming back to
52 room temperature. Next, they were field cooled (FC) to 20 K in a 2.5 T field. The
53 field was removed upon reaching 20 K, and the FC remanence was measured in zero
54 field on rewarming to room temperature. Then they were zero-field cooled (ZFC) to
55 20 K, given a low-temperature saturation isothermal remanent magnetization
56 (LTSIRM) in 2.5 T at 20 K, and measured in zero field during warming to room

57 temperature. We also applied a series of low-temperature remanence measurements on
58 four samples (two type A samples, one type B sample, and one type C sample) to test
59 for contribution of goethite. Following the RTSIRM cooling-warming cycles, the
60 same samples were removed from the MPMS and demagnetized using an alternating
61 field (AF) demagnetizer with a peak field of 200 mT to remove the signal carried by
62 ferromagnetic minerals with coercivities < 200 mT. The samples were then put back
63 in the MPMS and the remanence was measured from 300 K to 20 K. Next, the
64 samples were warmed up to 400 K, the Néel temperature of goethite, and then cooled
65 again to 20 K.

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67 Mössbauer spectra were obtained at the Institute for Rock Magnetism from four
68 samples (one type A sample, one type B sample, and two type C samples, [Table S5](#)) of
69 crushed bulk rock at both 295 K and 18 K. The measurements were performed with a
70 conventional constant-acceleration spectrometer in transmission geometry with a
71 source of ^{57}Co in an Rh matrix, with an activity of about 50 mCi. Hyperfine
72 parameters such as magnetic hyperfine field (B_{HF}), isomer shift (IS) and quadrupole
73 splitting (QS) have been determined with IRM in-house software, and $\alpha\text{-Fe}$ at room
74 temperature was used to calibrate isomer shifts and velocity scale. Scanning electron
75 microscopy (SEM) observation and Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDS)
76 analysis of 11 (two type A samples, six type B samples, three type C samples, [Table](#)
77 [S6](#)) sampled were acquired on a Field Electron and Ion GEG650 SEM, operating at
78 15 kV and 40–60 nA at the SEM lab at the Key Laboratory of Orogenic Belts and
79 Crustal Evolution, School of Earth and Space Sciences, Peking University (China).

80

81 Figure S1. Thermal demagnetization trajectories of additional type A and type C
 82 samples presented in this research. IS - in situ, circles - inclination, dots - declination.

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86 Figure S2. Thermal demagnetization trajectories of additional type B samples
 87 presented in this research. IS - in situ, circles - inclination, dots - declination.

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89 Figure S3. Hysteresis loops and component analysis of the isothermal remanent
 90 magnetization of the red bed samples at room temperature. Sample 14NQ1504 is
 91 adjacent to a dike and was baked with dark purple color, whereas unbaked samples
 92 are red.

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102 Figure S4. Plot of the room temperature hysteresis parameters (a), and magnetizations

103 of the FC vs. ZFC curves at 20 K (b). Lines in panel b are the FC/ZFC remanence

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14NQ0409 (type B)

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120 Figure S5. Low-temperature in-phase and quadrature AC susceptibility measured
 121 from 20 to 300 K at different frequencies (1.0, 5.6, 31.6, 177.9, and 997.3 Hz) for a
 122 type B red bed sample (a), and expanded view of quadrature susceptibilities,
 123 compared to the derivative of in-phase susceptibility with respect to $\ln(f)$.

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133 Figure S6. Normalized thermal decay curves of the red bed samples from the three
 134 types. Magnetization is the vector difference sum calculated using
 135 www.paleomagnetism.org [Koymans et al., 2016] to avoid the directional
 136 change-induced variation in absolute magnetization.

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Table S1. Hysteresis parameters of the Nangqian red beds.

Type	Sample	M_s	M_{rs}	B_c	B_{cr}	M_{rs}/M_s
		Am^2/kg	Am^2/kg	mT	mT	
A	14NQ0703	2.93E-03	1.58E-03	344.90	562.41	0.54
A	14NQ0712	3.07E-03	2.19E-03	321.30	464.38	0.71
A	14NQ0719	3.46E-03	2.60E-03	317.16	471.74	0.75
A	14NQ0910	3.25E-03	1.82E-03	240.34	399.73	0.56
A	14NQ1504	9.59E-03	4.53E-03	216.04	368.43	0.47
A	14NQ1509	7.66E-03	5.16E-03	267.30	381.57	0.67
A	14NQ1510	6.21E-03	3.33E-03	240.96	386.18	0.54
A	14NQ1513	6.28E-03	4.26E-03	266.69	390.42	0.68
A	15NQ5315	8.84E-03	5.70E-03	358.50	479.07	0.65
B	14NQ0409	4.07E-03	2.44E-03	271.90	473.70	0.60
B	14NQ0411	2.90E-03	1.73E-03	278.41	490.57	0.60
B	14NQ0602	6.19E-03	4.35E-03	259.84	374.40	0.70
B	14NQ0611	4.19E-03	2.86E-03	278.73	408.90	0.68
B	14NQ0915	4.15E-03	2.36E-03	243.19	401.54	0.57
B	14NQ1308	2.69E-03	1.95E-03	306.65	472.92	0.73
B	14NQ1309	4.03E-03	2.65E-03	250.97	419.68	0.66
B	15NQ5307	7.96E-03	5.47E-03	367.68	520.88	0.69
B	15NQ5308	5.49E-03	3.85E-03	322.48	459.83	0.70
B	15NQ5313	6.23E-03	4.01E-03	318.73	474.75	0.64
B	15NQ5314	7.73E-03	5.85E-03	378.14	487.94	0.76
B	15NQ5318	1.27E-03	8.31E-04	342.09	487.55	0.65
B	15NQ5321	5.93E-03	3.31E-03	262.52	410.43	0.56
B	15NQ5610	9.21E-03	5.31E-03	311.24	520.62	0.58
B	15NQ5611	8.24E-03	5.41E-03	347.50	519.62	0.66
B	15NQ5716	9.05E-03	5.40E-03	313.63	508.48	0.60
C	15NQ5403	6.70E-03	4.10E-03	291.09	483.93	0.61
C	15NQ5404	7.34E-03	4.61E-03	347.30	522.80	0.63
C	15NQ5405	6.27E-03	3.90E-03	306.77	512.04	0.62
C	15NQ5408	9.70E-03	7.00E-03	399.12	462.60	0.72
C	15NQ5412	6.69E-03	4.31E-03	331.06	517.46	0.64
C	15NQ5417	7.83E-03	5.09E-03	343.61	520.18	0.65
C	15NQ5505	5.12E-03	3.44E-03	260.89	487.71	0.67
C	15NQ5708	6.45E-03	4.06E-03	315.61	497.09	0.63
C	15NQ5709	6.00E-03	4.46E-03	369.45	442.08	0.74
C	15NQ5721	8.15E-03	5.04E-03	318.01	518.48	0.62

Note. B_c - coercive force; B_{cr} - remanent coercivity; M_{rs} - remanent saturation; M_s - saturation magnetization.

Table S2. Results of IRM component analysis.

Type	Sample	Component 1				Component 2			
		B_h	DP	OC.mean	EC.mean	B_h	DP	OC.mean	EC.mean
A	14NQ0703	105.80	3.34	0.15	0.14	688.58	1.76	0.85	0.86
A	14NQ0712	76.63	3.99	0.12	0.14	613.93	1.91	0.88	0.86
A	14NQ0719	85.63	3.63	0.13	0.13	640.25	2.03	0.87	0.87
A	14NQ0910	72.40	2.25	0.09	0.09	478.00	1.99	0.91	0.91
A	14NQ1504	90.99	1.96	0.06	0.05	476.32	1.91	0.94	0.95
A	14NQ1509	126.04	2.44	0.09	0.08	505.59	2.02	0.91	0.92
A	14NQ1510	66.72	2.36	0.07	0.06	460.28	2.09	0.93	0.94
A	14NQ1513	66.20	7.72	0.07	0.06	460.64	2.09	0.93	0.94
A	15NQ5315	-	-	-	-	570.17	2.00	1.00	1.00
B	14NQ0409	97.31	2.73	0.07	0.07	621.82	2.09	0.93	0.93
B	14NQ0602	52.63	5.56	0.11	0.11	513.87	2.09	0.89	0.89
B	14NQ0611	64.12	4.69	0.09	0.08	540.91	2.09	0.91	0.92
B	14NQ0915	53.07	2.51	0.09	0.06	582.11	2.37	0.91	0.94
B	14NQ1308	69.35	5.07	0.11	0.12	578.15	1.94	0.89	0.88
B	14NQ1309	79.77	1.82	0.05	0.04	635.38	2.30	0.95	0.96
B	15NQ5307	81.44	2.35	0.05	0.04	638.08	2.14	0.95	0.96
B	15NQ5308	81.93	2.06	0.05	0.04	669.40	2.25	0.95	0.96
B	15NQ5313	93.70	2.42	0.07	0.07	478.14	1.91	0.93	0.93
B	15NQ5314	-	-	-	-	588.15	2.04	1.00	1.00
B	15NQ5318	118.60	2.27	0.07	0.07	475.42	1.81	0.93	0.93
B	15NQ5321	66.59	2.33	0.08	0.08	439.48	2.00	0.92	0.92
B	15NQ5610	102.47	2.28	0.13	0.13	518.94	1.74	0.87	0.87
B	15NQ5611	97.78	2.35	0.10	0.10	490.46	1.76	0.90	0.90
B	15NQ5716	133.02	2.59	0.13	0.13	492.25	1.78	0.87	0.87
C	15NQ5405	102.91	2.35	0.12	0.12	520.73	1.77	0.88	0.88
C	15NQ5408	-	-	-	-	659.93	2.02	1.00	1.00
C	15NQ5417	114.73	2.28	0.11	0.11	506.72	1.74	0.89	0.89
C	15NQ5505	100.95	2.72	0.14	0.11	759.88	2.03	0.86	0.89
C	15NQ5708	88.33	2.68	0.08	0.09	463.51	1.82	0.92	0.91
C	15NQ5709	100.49	2.19	0.06	0.05	635.10	1.97	0.94	0.95
C	15NQ5721	86.16	1.98	0.17	0.17	368.36	1.62	0.83	0.83

Note. B_h - mean coercivity of an individual grain population; DP- dispersion parameter; OC.- observed contribution; EC.- extrapolated contribution.

Table S3 Lists of samples investigated for susceptibility vs. temperature experiment

Type	Sample
A	14NQ0703
A	14NQ0712
A	14NQ1504
A	14NQ1509
A	14NQ1510
B	14NQ0409
B	14NQ0411
B	14NQ0602
B	14NQ1309
B	15NQ5308
B	15NQ5318
C	15NQ5404
C	15NQ5408
C	15NQ5417
C	15NQ5505
C	15NQ5709
C	15NQ5721

Table S4. Remanent magnetization at 20 K after ZFC and FC treatment.

Type	Sample	M_{ZFC}	M_{FC}	M_{FC}/M_{ZFC}
		Am^2/kg	Am^2/kg	
A	14NQ0703	3.87E-03	9.70E-03	2.51
A	14NQ0712	2.19E-03	2.70E-03	1.23
A	14NQ1504	2.79E-03	9.48E-03	3.40
A	14NQ1509	6.10E-03	1.86E-02	3.05
A	14NQ1513	3.74E-03	7.63E-03	2.04
B	14NQ0409	1.90E-03	4.58E-03	2.42
B	14NQ0411	1.76E-03	4.95E-03	2.81
B	14NQ0602	2.83E-03	5.05E-03	1.79
B	14NQ0611	2.44E-03	4.26E-03	1.75
B	15NQ5308	3.64E-03	6.74E-03	1.85
B	15NQ5314	5.17E-03	9.30E-03	1.80
B	14NQ1309	2.79E-03	6.16E-03	2.21
B	14NQ1308	2.02E-03	3.01E-03	1.49
B	15NQ5318	4.83E-03	9.29E-03	1.92
C	15NQ5408	4.93E-03	5.15E-03	1.04
C	15NQ5412	4.98E-03	5.22E-03	1.05
C	15NQ5505	3.77E-03	4.13E-03	1.10
C	15NQ5709	4.62E-03	4.84E-03	1.05
C	15NQ5721	6.07E-03	6.36E-03	1.05

Table S5. Fitting results of the Mössbauer spectrum from four red bed samples.

Type	Sample	Temperature	IS ₍₁₎	QS ₍₁₎	B _{HF(1)}	Width ₍₁₎	Percentage ₍₁₎	B _{HF(1)} variation	IS ₍₂₎	QS ₍₂₎	B _{HF(2)}	Width ₍₂₎	Percentage ₍₂₎	B _{HF(2)} variation
			[K]	[mm/s]		[mm/s]	[T]	[mm/s]	[%]	[mm/s]		[mm/s]	[T]	[mm/s]
A	14NQ0703	295	0.42	-0.24	35.35	0.3	6.40	10.30	0.35	-0.21	50.98	0.39	42.15	-
		18	0.46	-0.25	49.94	0.3	28.67	1.77	0.47	-0.19	53.14	0.32	44.71	-
B	15NQ5318	295	0.42	-0.17	50.18	0.4	7.95	10.50	0.35	-0.21	51.20	0.31	37.73	-
		18	0.46	-0.24	49.99	0.3	23.81	2.32	0.46	-0.21	53.11	0.32	44.32	-
C	15NQ5412	295	0.37	-0.21	50.48	0.3	12.43	4.89	0.35	-0.21	51.21	0.30	44.84	-
		18	0.50	-0.17	54.30	0.3	0.00	3.90	0.47	-0.20	53.15	0.33	59.36	-
C	15NQ5505	295	0.35	-0.21	50.04	0.3	8.38	3.89	0.35	-0.21	51.23	0.32	42.76	-
		18	0.46	-0.14	53.60	0.3	0.00	3.90	0.47	-0.20	53.13	0.32	52.93	-

Note. IS- isomer shift; QS-quadrupole splitting; B_{HF}- magnetic hyperfine field.

Table S6. Lists samples applied SEM and EDS examinations.

Type	Sample
A	14NQ0712
A	14NQ1504
B	14NQ0315
B	14NQ0411
B	14NQ0602
B	14NQ0905
B	14NQ1309
B	15NQ5314
C	15NQ5408
C	15NQ5709
C	15NQ5723